

Summary

The following project is a study on “**Assessing Spatio-Temporal Precipitation Variability and Extreme Events in India**” which highlights the critical need to understand fluctuations in extreme precipitation events due to anthropogenic climate change across various regions and across time within India. Through the study we aim to understand the degree and the number of extreme precipitation events. We have utilized the Mann-Kendall trend line to visualize the trends, indicating a positive trend for both spatial and temporal variability. The study informs flood risk preparation, water management, and climate policies, all of which contribute to the ongoing discussion of the effects of climate change. In conclusion, the statistical significance of our findings suggest that further research is needed that could help with developing early warning systems, infrastructure development and overall policy making to anticipate and thwart the effects of extreme precipitation.